

Zinc triflate a water compatible, green catalyst in one pot three-component efficient synthesis of α -amino nitriles

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Abstract : α -Amino nitriles are synthesized in one pot three-component coupling of aldehydes, amines and trimethylsilyl cyanide using catalytic amount of zinc triflate at ambient temperature.

Keywords : α -Amino nitriles, zinc triflate, aldehydes, amines, trimethylsilyl cyanide.

Introduction

α -Amino nitriles are key intermediates for the synthesis of a variety of vital molecules like amino acids¹, thiadiazoles², imidazoles³ and bioactive molecules like Saframycin A⁴ etc. Due to their large number of synthetic utilities their efficient preparation is of great significance and continues to draw attention of organic chemists. The traditional method of their production is Strecker reaction⁵ which involves use of established toxic KCN. Apparently some improvements were necessary keeping in view these crucial synthons. Therefore, some alternative cyanide transferring agents have been explored like diethyl phosphorocyanidate⁶, α -trimethylsiloxy nitriles⁷, acetone cyanohydrin⁸ (of course it requires alkaline medium which may or may not be suitable), Et_2AlCN ⁹ and trimethylsilyl cyanide¹⁰ etc. Out of these non-alkali metal cyanide variants trimethylsilyl cyanide continues to be more attractive, safer and effective cyanide source for nucleophilic addition of cyanide ion to imines. Also for these new developments a catalyst would be needed to polarize imine bond effectively and splitting of various cyanide ion from various sources. To achieve this objective various Bronsted and Lewis acids are reported like H_2SO_4 and its derivatives $\text{SiO}_2 : \text{H}_2\text{SO}_4$ ^{11a}, $\text{NH}_2\text{SO}_3\text{H}$ ^{11b} and Lewis acids like, InCl_3 ^{11c}, $\text{La}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ or $\text{GdCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ^{11d} etc. and other strong Lewis acids^{11e-h}. These existing procedures have several limitations such as acid catalysts used are corrosive in nature and are also

expensive. In addition to that some of them are hygroscopic in nature and difficult to handle. Over and above these limitations several of these form corrosive and hazardous by-products during aqueous work-up. Obviously there is enough scope for further improvement in these synthetic procedures of α -amino nitriles.

Applications of zinc triflate in organic synthesis is of current interest because of its advantages over conventional Lewis acids as they can be recovered and recycled which are preconditions of green chemistry. These catalysts are inexpensive in comparison to other metal triflates. Conventional Lewis acids often leave residues and their waste disposal is also critical and can cause serious environmental problems. In contrast, metal triflates are considered to be environmental benign and are also readily accessible commercially or they can be prepared in the laboratory and their waste/residues are not at all hazardous. Zinc triflate have been successfully used for the synthesis of pyrazino[2,1-*b*]quinazoline-3,6-diones¹², stereoselective Mannich-type reaction¹³, chemoselective conversion of ethers to the corresponding benzoates¹⁴. Synthesis of pyrazolines via arylhydrazones¹⁵, deoxygenation of organic *N*-oxides¹⁶ etc. In continuation to our own investigation¹⁶ on zinc triflate as mild Lewis acid, here we wish to report its use in the synthesis of amino nitriles in a one pot three-component coupling of aldehydes, amines and trimethylsilyl cyanide at room temperature (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

Results and discussion

In a typical case, a mixture of benzaldehyde (10 mmol), aniline (10 mmol), trimethylsilyl cyanide (10 mmol) and zinc triflate (1 mmol) in acetonitrile (15 mL) was stirred at room temperature for 45 min. Product 2-(*N*-anilino)-2-phenylacetonitrile (**3a**), with m.p. 72–73 °C was obtained in 95% yield. In spectral analysis, **3a** showed absorption at 2240 cm^{-1} for $\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$ function. A broad singlet (D_2O exchangeable) was observed for NH in ^1H NMR spectrum of **3a** beside with other peaks. Similarly, other aldehydes were coupled with a variety of amines and

trimethylsilyl cyanide in presence of catalytic amount of zinc triflate to furnish α -amino nitriles **3b-p** in 81–96% yields (Table 1). The products thus obtained were characterized with IR, NMR and mass spectra.

A variety of aromatic, conjugated and heterocyclic aldehydes have been reacted with amines and TMS-CN at room temperature to obtain α -amino nitriles (Table 1). Secondary amines such as morpholine, piperidine, pyrrolidine have also been employed along with aromatic amines. These reactions were completed in 45–65 min and 10 mol % catalyst was sufficient. The use of large

Table 1. Zinc triflate mediated synthesis of α -amino nitriles

Entry	Aldehydes	Amines	Products ^a	Time (min)	Yields (%) ^b	m.p. (°C) ^c
1			3a	45	95	72–73 (72–73)
2			3b	60	88	120–122 (121–122)
3			3c	55	90	74–76 (74–76)
4			3d	50	96	Colorless oil
5			3e	55	85	Colorless oil
6			3f	65	88	68–70 (68–70)
7			3g	55	89	Colorless oil
8			3h	55	90	95–96 (95–96)

Table-1 (contd.)

9		3i	45	96	109-111 (109-112)	
10		3j	55	90	Colorless oil	
11		3k	65	88	128-129 (128-129)	
12		3l	55	85	108-110	
13		3m	55	86	117-118	
14		3n	55	82	101-102	
15		3o	65	81	84-85	
16		3p	60	85	Colorless oil	

^aThe products were characterized by comparison of their melting points and spectral (IR, ¹H NMR) data with those of authentic samples. ^bIsolated yields after recrystallization. ^cLit. m.p. in parenthesis.

amount of catalyst did not improve the yields or reduce the reaction time. Also, when reaction was carried out without catalyst, the reaction did not proceed efficiently. It is worth mentioning here we did not observe the formation of any ring ruptured dyes as is observed in the past rather nitriles are obtained in good yields. Certainly, during Schiff's base formation zinc triflate did not rupture the furan ring¹⁷ as the furan ring is very much sensitive to acids as well as bases.

Difficulties are always encountered when conjugated α -amino nitriles are to be produced. The conventional procedure produces alkaline medium and hence these methods are plagued with the formation of solvolysed or rearranged products¹⁸. This may due to solvents employed such as alcohol, water etc. in these methods. In contrast in this procedure neither double bond migration is observed nor the formations of any solvolysed product rather normal nitriles are obtained in excellent yields.

In conclusion, the present protocol employing catalytic amount of zinc triflate, is an efficient and superior

to already reported procedures, as it is mild, cost effective and one pot strategy for the preparation of α -amino nitriles. Further advantages of this protocol are less time, high yields and work is simple and non hazardous. Also the present procedure is fairly general and is applicable to a variety of aromatic, conjugated and heterocyclic aldehydes which are *in situ* coupled with primary, secondary and aromatic amines and trimethylsilyl cyanide at room temperature. Products are obtained in excellent yields in short reaction time. Needless to say during work-up no hazardous/unsafe by-products were formed in this new method being reported. Triflate used in this efficient protocol is cheaper than lanthanide triflates and secondly, they are not as moisture sensitive as Sc(OTf)₃.

Experimental

Melting points were determined in open capillaries and are uncorrected. Reagent grade chemicals were purchased from commercial source and used without further purification. IR spectra were recorded in KBr discs on a

Perkin-Elmer 240C analyzer. ^1H NMR spectra were recorded on Varian Gemini 300 (300 MHz) spectrometer using TMS as internal standard. The progress of the reaction was monitored by thin layer chromatography (TLC) using silica gel G (Merck).

General procedure for preparation of α -amino nitriles :

A mixture of aldehyde (2 mmol), amine (2 mmol), trimethylsilyl cyanide (2 mmol) and zinc triflate (0.2 mmol) in acetonitrile (15 mL) was stirred at room temperature for time indicated in Table 1. After reaction completion (vide TLC), excess of acetonitrile was evaporated under reduced pressure and residue thus obtained was extracted with diethyl ether (3 \times 20 mL). The organic layer was washed with saturated solution of NaHCO_3 (2 \times 20 ml), brine, and dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 . Evaporation of solvent gave crude product which was purified by recrystallization with benzene : petroleum ether mixture.

Selected spectral data for 2-(N-anilino)-2-phenylacetonitrile (3a) :

IR (KBr) : 3345, 2238 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 7.53 (2H, m), 7.30 (3H, t), 7.28 (2H, t, J 7.9 Hz), 6.90 (1H, t, J 7.6 Hz), 6.77 (2H, d, J 7.9 Hz), 5.41 (1H, s), 4.13 (1H, br s); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 146.5, 136.5, 130.7, 129.9, 128.5, 128.2, 127.1, 122.7, 117.7, 51.2.

Selected spectral data for 2-phenyl-2-(N-pyrrolidino)-acetonitrile (3e) :

IR (KBr) : 2230 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 7.54–7.43 (2H, m), 7.41–7.29 (3H, m), 4.47 (1H, s), 2.72–2.61 (4H, m), 1.90–1.69 (4H, m); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 135.7, 129.6, 129.1, 128.3, 117.8, 110.5, 60.3, 52.8.

Selected spectral data for 2-(N-morpholino)-2-phenylacetonitrile (3f) :

IR (KBr) : 2235 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 7.48–7.27 (5H, m), 4.74 (4H, t, J 4.5 Hz), 2.59 (4H, t, J 4.5 Hz); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 133.7, 130.7, 129.5, 129.3, 128.5, 116.5, 72.5, 62.3, 53.9.

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